

ReBioCycle in a nutshell

ReBioCycle provides a portfolio of advanced bio-plastic sorting and recycling technologies for bio-based biodegradable plastics within **three complementary waste-processor-centric hubs** at a demonstration scale located in **Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands.**

The Hubs

These hubs operate in real-world environments to efficiently recycle three types of bioplastics: PLA, PHA, and composites. The Hubs will provide **Real-World Demonstrations** and showcase our novel recycling solutions.

Project coordinator

University College Dublin,
BiOrbic Bioeconomy SFI
Research Centre
Kevin O'Connor

Project duration

4 years
1 October 2024 –
30 September 2028

Visit our website
and our Social
Media channels:

www.rebiocycle.eu

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ReBioCycle

A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

HUB Leader:

"Novamont, part of Versalis (Eni), brings decades of expertise in biodegradable and compostable bioplastics from fully or partially renewable sources. This positions us to thoroughly analyse bioplastic properties, test recycling methods, and ensure the best sustainable solutions for each bioplastic application and setting a new sustainability standard."

Orsola Bolognani, Strategic Planning and Corporate Communication, Senior Program Manager, NOVAMONT

NOVAMONT
A Versalis Company

Partners

Iren Group

I. BLU, IREN Group

AMIAT,
IREN Group

IT HUB Material Flow Overview

Italy

The Italian Hub will focus on chemical technology, upscaling it to TRL 7. NOVAMONT leads the Italian Hub. NOVAMONT technology will be used to recycle 600 kg of mixed composites to achieve rComposites for flexible and rigid packaging with a 15% recycled content. rPHA from the Dutch and Spanish Hub will be tested in the Italian hub to blend into bioplastic formulations.

The IREN Group waste sorting site of Borgaro Torinese (Piedmont, Italy) and NOVAMONT's new dedicated bioplastics recycling section within its Terni (IT) plant, will be involved, together with AMIAT and I.BLU.

Input:

Mixed composites from municipal source, separated plastic waste with 1% bioplastics.

Processes:

Chemical recycling.

Outputs Available:

rComposites with a 15% recycled content Blends with rPHA received from the Dutch and Spanish Hub.

IT HUB Map

